

Beyond 5G Artificial Intelligence Assisted Energy Efficient Open Radio Access Network

BeGREEN Deliverable 6.1

Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination of the Results

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Editor(s):	Oriol Sallent (UPC)
Author(s):	Revaz Berozashvili (ACC) Simon Pryor (ACC), Oriol Sallent (UPC) Mir Ghoraishi (GIGASYS)
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List of Acronyms

AI	Artificial Intelligence
B5G	Beyond 5G
EuCNC	European Conference on Networks and Communications
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
ICC	International Conference on Communications
MIMO	Multiple-input multiple-output
ML	Machine Learning
OFC	Optical Fibre Communication
ONDM	Optical Network Design and Modelling
OPEX	Operational Expenses
RAN	Radio Access Network
RIS	Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces
SDO	Standards Development Organisation

Executive Summary

The primary aim of BeGREEN D6.1, “Plans for Exploitation and Dissemination of the Results2’ is to describe the project plan on dissemination and communication actions, the individual and joint exploitation activities, the envisaged liaisons and the standardization contribution plan.

This plan considers all the activities related to the promotion of the BeGREEN project and its results beyond the project own community. This also includes the dissemination of BeGREEN contributions in a way that is easily understood by a non-specialist audience, e.g., the media and the general public.

The dissemination plan includes activities boosting awareness of BeGREEN results in the scientific community, working on the same research field. In general, this will be carried out through publications in high impact journals/magazines, and participation and organization of technical events. This document also identifies relevant open-source activities to be developed along the project execution.

The exploitation plan covers activities aiming at using the results in further research activities other than those covered by the project, such as developing, creating and marketing products or processes, creating and providing a service. This activity is just started and the original plans will need to get evolved as the project tasks continue. BeGREEN Innovation Manager is working with partners to mature this plan.

The standardization plan seeks to ensure that the key concepts of the BeGREEN contributions are proposed and adopted in the relevant standards. The project has already established a standardisation advisory committee who is working on a comprehensive roadmap towards achieving project’s targets in this regard.

The plans presented in this deliverable will be updated during the next few months. The updated plan will be reported in the next deliverables, together with the reporting of the activities, in D6.2 (M12) “Interim Report on Exploitation”, D6.3 (M13) “Interim Report on Dissemination and Communication”, and D6.4 (M18) “Interim Report on Standardisation Contributions”.

1 Introduction

BeGREEN benefits from a strong consortium and leadership and is committed to an ambitious Europe-wide rollout of results into the Beyond 5G (B5G) marketplace following the project. The dissemination and exploitation strategy will set the basis, channels, and guidelines to target specific groups covering a wide range of audience, including industry partners, academia, public authorities, standardisation bodies, and end-users. This will maximise the project outreach ensuring exploitation activities through and after the project's life span. To maximise the social, economic, and technical benefits of the proposed novel technologies, maximum priority will be given to Standards Development Organisations (SDOs) and stakeholders' impact. The dissemination, standardization, communication, exploitation, and stakeholders' engagement plans will be the pillars of the strategy, as they will include a range of activities, events, dissemination opportunities and guidelines on how to communicate about the project, as well as KPIs to monitor the relevance and performance of the activities carried out. These plans will include details on specific activities on a national, European, and global levels. BeGREEN partners are frontrunners in 5G network and infrastructure development and deployment. They have an in-depth knowledge of their respective markets and will therefore be key players in exploiting the results locally and nationally, and to anticipate important business opportunities from BeGREEN. The strategy will not only look to activities and opportunities during the entire project lifetime but will also draft plans and guidelines for further exploitation of the results and lessons learnt. All partners in the consortium will contribute to compile a list of relevant events, national activities, and external projects, and will look at possible opportunities to present the project and set cooperation agreements with external initiatives and organisations.

1.1 Scope of the document

This document describes BeGREEN's plan for exploitation and dissemination of the results. It provides the project plan on dissemination actions and communication activities and tools in Section 2, the standardization contribution plan in Section 3, envisaged liaisons in Section 4, and finally the individual and joint exploitation activities in Section 5.

2 Dissemination and Communication Plan

Dissemination activities allow the diffusion of scientific results generated within the project. These results might be of different nature and have different types of target audience. In turn, going beyond the specialised target audience primarily considered in the dissemination activities, BeGREEN has devised a strategy of communicating its concept and results to a wide non-specialised audience. A proper communication strategy is essential to broadly inform about the developments and future impacts of the work carried out in BeGREEN. It is of paramount importance to bring closer the benefits of B5G to the administrations and to the general public, conveying the message that they will be beneficial from both economic and societal perspective.

At this stage, BeGREEN has defined a careful plan of activities to be performed, including specific measurable objectives, as described in the following. Furthermore, for each envisaged action, the different types of target audience have been identified.

2.1 Project logo

The first task in the communication and dissemination of the main activities carried out by BeGREEN is the definition of a unique identifier that easily allows the target audience to identify the project. For that reason, the BeGREEN consortium has established a dedicated logo for the project as Figure 2-1 shows. This logo is included in all the BeGREEN communication channels, deliverables, presentation slides, leaflets, posters, etc.

Figure 2-1 BeGREEN project logo

2.2 Internal communications: Microsoft Teams repository and collaboration tool

For internal communications between partners and as a repository for the project documents and notes, BeGREEN consortium uses Microsoft Teams workspace. By using this tool, partners are enabled to exchange materials: document library, deliverables, partner's information, etc., as well as to enjoy the topic specific channels for message exchange, wiki, and teleconferencing. The aim of this repository is to ease the organization of the internal work throughout the project lifetime. Figure 2-2 and Figure 2-3 show screenshots of the BeGREEN's Teams repository and currently available topic specific channels.

Figure 2-2 BeGREEN's MS Teams repository

Figure 2-3 BeGREEN's MS Teams channel

2.3 Project website

BeGREEN will host a comprehensive, regularly updated, public website. It will contain all relevant project information such as the global vision and objectives, its relation to 6GIA, SNS (5GPPP) and other projects in the same domain, and the BeGREEN consortium. The site will provide access to the public deliverables of BeGREEN, as well as standardisation results, publications, and public materials, such as flyers, posters and other collateral. The site news channel will provide an overview of BeGREEN events and other relevant events. A database, under General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) guidelines, will be built and a newsletter will be sent every four months on average.

The official webpage address is (www.sns-begreen.com), the design has gone through last comments and will be online in the next days. Figure 2-4, and Figure 2-5 present the main page and its project description section, and Figure 2-6 shows the news section. The webpage is ready to go online any days after few remaining corrections are performed by the developers.

Figure 2-4 BeGREEN webpage main page screenshot

Figure 2-5 BeGREEN webpage: project description section

Figure 2-6 BeGREEN webpage news section: blog posts and project tweets (preview)

Website content will be regularly updated and maintained until the end of the project by all the partners of BeGREEN consortium. To ease accessibility, the website content has been split in the following sections:

- Home: It is the main page of BeGREEN website, which enables an easier browsing of the website content. It also contains links to the social media channels (see Section 2.4).
- About: It contains an overall description of this project, gathering the BeGREEN vision, concept, innovation, demonstrators and impact.
- News: Includes relevant news and blog posts about BeGREEN activities and results, which will also be spread through the BeGREEN social media channels to increase the project visibility.
- Deliverables: Publishes all of the project's public deliverables.
- Dissemination: It all disseminations including publications, talks and events, open source contributions as well as the project's contributions to the standardisation activities.
- Consortium: It provides a description of each partner of BeGREEN consortium.
- Contact: It contains a contact form to send a message to the project coordinator, project manager, and technical coordinator for all relevant communications with the BeGREEN consortium.

To measure the impact of BeGREEN project website, we collect performance statistics such as: number of users visiting the website, number of sessions, average session duration, bounce rate, etc.

2.4 Social media

The BeGREEN website will be assisted by exploiting different social networking groups, e.g., Twitter, LinkedIn, etc. BeGREEN will further host a YouTube/webcasting channel that periodically broadcasts about the project, and a LinkedIn group to post the project activities. All the project social media accounts can be accessed from the project website and target to have at least 100-200 followers by the end of the project. The actions carried out in each social media account are briefly described in the following sections.

2.4.1 Twitter

Twitter is one of the most popular social networks and is widely used by the scientific community as a tool to communicate their results. In the same way as other SNS and previous 5G-PPP projects, BeGREEN has already set up a Twitter account (https://twitter.com/SNS_BeGREEN) with the aim of providing information about the ongoing activities throughout the project lifetime. Figure 2-7 shows a screenshot of the main BeGREEN Twitter page.

Figure 2-7 BeGREEN project Twitter account

2.4.2 LinkedIn

LinkedIn has established itself as a business and employment-oriented social network. Since LinkedIn is tailored for professionals, it is well suited to communicate the activities and contributions carried out in BeGREEN project. To that end, BeGREEN project management has created a project specific page (<https://www.linkedin.com/in/sns-begreen-project-613259250/>) whose main purpose is to open BeGREEN target audience. The LinkedIn page intends to foster discussions on relevant aspects of the project, advertise news and events, and collect stakeholder’ opinions. Figure 2-8 shows a screenshot of the LinkedIn page.

Figure 2-8 BeGREEN project LinkedIn account

2.4.3 YouTube

YouTube is the most popular video-sharing platform in the world, thus it is the perfect social channel to broadcast the main activities carried out in the project. For that reason, BeGREEN hosts a YouTube channel that provides video content produced by the project to stakeholders at this address (<https://www.youtube.com/@snsbegreen>). Figure 2-9 shows BeGREEN's YouTube channel.

Figure 2-9 BeGREEN YouTube channel

2.4.4 Partners social channels

In addition to the project specific social media channel, BeGREEN consortium partners are encouraged to post related news and breakthroughs of the project regularly. Figure 2-10 shows an example.

Figure 2-10 Example of dissemination of BeGREEN news via partner (Accelleran) LinkedIn page

2.5 Scientific publications in leading conferences and journals

To generate awareness and induce constructive comments and feedback from the scientific and industrial research community, BeGREEN will target high-level IEEE conferences and peer-reviewed journals related to the project's topics. The targeted conferences are, amongst others, the European Conference on Networks

and Communications (EuCNC), IEEE Globecom, International Conference on Communications (ICC), ACM Mobicom. We will also target top peer-reviewed journals, including, amongst others, IEEE Communications Magazine, and IEEE Transaction on Networking. The project targets to have more than 10 publications submitted per year in such journals and/or conferences. BeGREEN partners will organise own events and get speaking slots at important conferences and exhibitions. Where possible, the project will take advantage of partners' or European Commission presence at international or regional events. A set of presentation slides, relevant graphics and posters will be prepared to support consortium partners in such activities.

In order to raise awareness within the consortium about dissemination opportunities in relevant conferences, an excel file named 'BeGREEN Dissemination Opportunities' and containing a list of upcoming conferences has been created and uploaded in BeGREEN's repository. It will be periodically updated. The project also creates a 'Dissemination Tracking Tool', to be an excel file for keeping the record of all project disseminations with details about each.

In this respect, a first action of the project has been to develop a paper entitled "BeGREEN: Beyond 5G Energy Efficient Networking by Hardware Acceleration and AI-Driven Management of Network Functions", which has been submitted to EuCNC'23. This paper introduces the project overall architecture and objectives.

2.6 Organization of highly directed workshops

BeGREEN members are very active and feature a vast expertise in organising flagship conference workshops and special sessions in the technical areas of the project. For example, members of the project organized workshops in the last three EuCNCs. Following this consolidated strategy, BeGREEN will take the lead in organizing at least one international workshop (possibly with collaboration with other projects), as a premiere opportunity to present project results in a very interactive and formal environment.

In this respect, a first initiative of the project has been to submit a Workshop proposal to EuCNC'23 together with some other projects (namely, BRAINE -H2020-ECSEL-2019-2-RIA-, VERGE -HORIZON-JU-SNS-2022-STREAM-A-01-05-, ACES - HORIZON-CL4-2022-DATA-01- and SmartEdge - HORIZON-CL4-2022-DATA-01). The goal of this workshop is to discuss the close synergy between Artificial Intelligence (AI) and edge computing, as two key enabling technologies shaping 6G, and identify the roadmap for more holistic, sustainable and future-proof design of AI- and edge-enabled solutions. The workshop will also focus on how AI can be leveraged to optimise the Radio Access Network (RAN) configuration from an application perspective in order to provide energy consumption savings.

2.7 Participation in 5G/B5G initiatives

The members of the consortium have been, and are very active, in organizing journal special issues related to the BeGREEN research areas. These constitute very important forums for presenting the achieved results to the scientific and industrial communities.

Similarly, the BeGREEN project members are highly involved in international programme committees and editorial boards of key conferences and journals. Examples of program committees and editorial boards project members are involved in are: International Conference on Optical Network Design and Modelling (ONDM), Optical Fiber Communication Conference (OFC), and EuCNC.

BeGREEN members' participation in joint initiatives among related projects in the ICT program is anticipated. BeGREEN will take the initiative to make a cluster of related topic projects to boost publicising the project activities and the dissemination of the results.

2.8 Industry exhibitions

Booth exhibitions and expert panels at EuCNC, presence at Mobile World Congress (2023-2025), 5G World,

5G Week, O-RAN related events.

2.9 Dissemination through training and personal mobility

BeGREEN will increase the number of students trained in the areas covered by the project. MSc or PhD students working in the project will carry their ideas into their future workplaces and academic institutions, thus increasing the reach of BeGREEN impact.

In this respect, a first initiative of the project has been the seminar “The Way to 6G”, which was held from 24th to 30th January 2023 at UPC premises in Barcelona. It took advantage of the no-classes period after termination of first semester exams’ and initiation of second semester. A total of 16 students registered to the seminar, which was lectured along 5 days with 4 or 5 hours per day, totalling 22 hours. The seminar addressed the way from 5G to Beyond 5G and eventually 6G through the major technological components envisaged in this roadmap. Students gained awareness about the relevance of involving energy-efficiency principles across the system design.

2.10 Open source activities

The project is committed to develop open source solutions and data set for the sake of roader community benefit. The potential item considered is AI/Machine Learning (ML) models, intent-engine, and the related data sets where it applies. A comprehensive strategy towards open source activities will be prepared and applied.

2.11 Target KPIs

Table 2-1 presents the list of target KPIs that BeGREEN has established for the different identified actions. It is planned that the achievements in dissemination/communication will periodically be gathered and confronted against the targets. The status will be discussed among the partners in WP6-specific calls in order to drive future actions.

Table 2-1 BeGREEN’s targets on dissemination and communication

Type of action	Target KPI	Audience
Website & social media	At least 2 newsletters per year, targeting at least 200 followers on Twitter and LinkedIn, 3000 access to website, 10 videos posted on YouTube channel	Wide public
Scientific publications	At least 15	Research community
Organisation of highly directed workshops	At least 2 workshops as organisers (1 as lead) At least 3 workshops as participants	Research community, Communications industry, Vertical users
Participation in 5G/B5G initiatives	At least 5 participations	Communications industry
Industry exhibitions	At least participation in 10 industrial events with project visibility	Communications industry, Vertical users
Dissemination through training and personal mobility	At least 3 actions	Research community
Datasets published	At least 2	Research community

3 Standardisation Plan

The project has set the following four objectives for the standardization activities:

1. Create a 'Standardisation Advisory Committee' (SAC) from project partners standardization experts
2. Create and maintain a project standardization activity roadmap. This roadmap will capture the standardization activities that may influence or get influenced by the project technological innovations. It will keep track of existing or upcoming industry specifications or recommendations that may affect the project technological choices and identify opportunities for the project to contribute its proposed solutions to present and future standardization groups.
3. Disseminate the project into the standardization forums to raise awareness and help create an opportunity for standardization exploitation.
4. Contribute through the partners (individually or jointly) with project-related technology proposals into the relevant standardization forums.

The project's SAC was created during the first month of the project and the kick off meeting was held on February 21, 2023. The plan is to have monthly calls to accomplish the committee's planned targets. According to the above targets, SAC is responsible for:

- Setting up the standardization activity roadmap within the first few months of the project roadmap and continuing to update this roadmap as the work in the project and these SDOs progress,
- Coordinating the project and standardization groups through constant monitoring of activities and regular conference calls with standardization experts,
- Seizing opportunities to push contributions into ongoing specifications,
- Coordinating with standardization experts to draft contributions ahead of standard meetings, and,
- Continuously promoting the project at standardization-related workshops, panels, and summits.

The above objectives remain applicable over the whole project duration. With focus on Year 1, it is anticipated that the activities will first involve the creation of the project standardization activity roadmap. As the design of the project solutions progresses, we anticipate seeing more efforts spent on standardization dissemination and contributions.

A preliminary identification of the relevant SDOs and work items, and their timeline according to the BeGREEN's life time was prepared during the proposal drafting. Figure 3-1 shows the outcome of this analysis. This figure will be updated with more accurate analysis of each relevant SDO and work item timeline, aiming at raising the conscious among partners' researchers active in BeGREEN towards the standardisation activities, and identifying suitable venues to contribute.

BeGREEN partners have a good footprint in the standardisation bodies, and a preliminary analysis of the partners roles in the project interactions with the SDOs has been proposed, but it is under discussion and will be confirmed during the coming SAC meetings.

Figure 3-1 BeGREEN preliminary SDO identification

4 Liaisons Plan

BeGREEN is aiming to actively collaborate with other SNS and 6GIA projects given the framework of collaboration (Collaboration Agreement) that is being prepared and will be signed by the consortium it is expected to be the case for other consortiums. In such framework the information exchange and other sorts of interactions with peer projects are easily achievable.

BeGREEN consortium are experienced as they have been active in the community for the past years in 5GPPP projects. Active liaison with SNS and 5GPPP activities, and the interactions with other projects within this framework is led by the Project Manager from BeGREEN side. Table 4-1 shows each partners participation in the SNS and 5GPPP working groups. The project has nominated representatives in the Steering Board (Coordinator and Project Manager), and Technology Board (Technical Coordinator and Project Manager) that will represent the project at SB and TB meetings and contribute fully to actions to determine the progress against the Performance KPIs. As it is observed in Table 4-1, the project already has representatives in each working group to channelise the project contributions, and in occasions, edit position papers, deliverables and reports from the working groups, proactively driving working groups closely related to their project goals.

Table 4-1 BeGREEN consortium participation in SNS and 5GPPP working groups

6GIA/5GPPP WG	Steering Board	Technical Board	Architecture WG	Trials WG	SME WG	Open SNS WG	Pre-Standardisation WG	Vision and Societal Challenge WG	TMV WG	Security WG
GIGASYS	*	*	*	*	*	*	*			
Accelleran					*					
I2CAT		*				*				
LMI			*	*		*				
TSA						*	*	*	*	*
IHP										
NEC			*			*				
REL						*				

5 Exploitation Plan

An adequate business and exploitation strategy is important to achieve a short- and long-term impact throughout the duration of the project and beyond. Among the main tasks to be fulfilled, the following stand out: a continuous seek of innovative business models in the different areas of development especially by use case partners in their verticals, a continuous market analysis and identification of novel services and applications for the considered vertical users, and assurance of sustainability and viability of the solutions and of the identified business models. To properly wrap around these activities, monitoring and systematic validation of all of them are essential to ensure a high impact during and beyond the action. A special task has been set up in WP6 to track these activities. In addition, a dedicated project milestone (MS4), set at month two, will ensure that D6.1 'Plan for exploitation and dissemination of project results' is finalized and, therefore, that a proper and effective plan for exploiting the project results is in place, both at the project- and at the singular partner-level.

At the outset of the project the consortium partners, all of which are committed to contribute according to their expertise and profile, have the following ambitions for exploitation of the results of BeGREEN project.

5.1 Individual exploitation plans

BT is both the operator of the largest public mobile network in the UK under the EE brand and has a BT Enterprise division that provides telecommunications services to other commercial organisations. BT Enterprise customers include other public mobile network operators through the supply of backhaul/fronthaul connectivity and physical base-station infrastructure provision including neutral host. In addition, a growing market of private mobile networks are targeted by BT Enterprise. As a public operator, BT will use the output of BeGREEN to minimise power cost Operational Expenses (OPEX) through energy efficiency. This will be achieved, where appropriate, by influencing standards and RAN equipment vendors, selecting equipment that meets the energy efficiency capability that will be established in BeGREEN and, through the availability of the RIC, deploying algorithms capable of optimising energy efficiency for the specific BT customer base. As a supplier to public and private network operators, BT will use the knowledge gained through BeGREEN to define new connectivity and telecommunication service products, including for example the deployment of Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces (RIS). The ability to provide energy optimised solutions for private networks will also support growth of the BT market share.

TSA plans to use the knowledge acquired from BeGREEN in the definition of the future network architectures, with the focus on provisioning novel wireless services. It will also provide a realistic overview of the maturity of the different technological components that should be available, facilitating the identification of cooperation opportunities to speed up their development. TSA plans to involve its industrial partners and stakeholders in the design of technically feasible and scalable commercial products from the project concepts. TSA will also explore new business opportunities in the private wireless networks based on positioning and cell-free network topologies, for example in factory environments and event locations. The target group/audience/stakeholder is the Telecommunication industry, industrial deployments, internal management and researchers. The expected results/expected impact are Scientific and technological expertise and patent applications.

LMI will use BeGREEN results to foster the growth of its Innovation department focused on energy saving in future RAN developments. LMI have a goal to include the outcome of this project to promote energy efficiency in our development plans and new energy efficiency features in 5G and 6G as well as propose new standards in energy efficiency.

ARM will use BeGREEN as an Innovation platform to maximize the power saving and efficiency of current generation (5G) and learn and develop strategies for next (5G/6G). Power saving and energy efficient are

the corner stone of Arm CPU architecture. With the learning/Blueprint/PoC achieved in BeGREEN, ARM can influence its eco-system to adhere and/or take cue from the BeGREEN research.

PW is one of the pioneers in accelerating the global O-RAN movement, building wireless networks around the world with their in-house software and hardware solutions. BeGREEN output will be used by PW for significant simplification in term of cost and power consumption focusing on effective solutions, specifically for the upcoming multiuser Multiple-Input Multiple-Output (MIMO). PW intends to convert the vast majority of the PHY processing (which gets higher and higher with multiuser MIMO) to very low CPU consuming process with efficient GPU based acceleration. Accordingly, the results and based on the advanced outputs of BeGREEN, PW will develop and productize RU offload HW and SW solution (TRL9) and will make it commercially available leveraging best fit COTS GPU-based accelerators.

NEC plans to use the results and findings from BeGREEN to improve its current RIS product prototypes and evolve its data-driven product portfolio taking into account the benefits of AI and ML to optimize energy efficiency for AI services. In this way, BeGREEN will have an impact on NEC's Mobile Radio Access Networks and Mobile Wireless Networking business units, specifically, on O-RAN compliant virtualized RAN products and NEC's advanced analytics platform for next-generation OSS. The project results will be used to demonstrate how it is possible to leverage developed innovations to optimize the energy consumption to both NEC development groups and potential customers, e.g., European network operators.

I2CAT will focus its exploitation on the O-RAN related assets developed in the project. I2CAT will continue developing an initial O-RAN SMO and non-RT RIC that has been developed through previous 5GPPP projects adding the energy optimisation concepts developed in BeGREEN. Market exploitation of this software asset will be pursued through license transfer agreements. In particular, I2CAT has a spin-off company Neutroon (www.neutroon.com) that is interested in bringing to the market O-RAN related developments. Additional exploitation of the project results will come through the use of these results in subsequent R&D projects belonging to the phase 2 of the SNS program.

IHP will focus its exploitation on developing further the work on JCAS and to integrate the solutions in the different platforms available internally. Resulting JCAS HW cores and SW implementations can be exploited together with the platforms via IHP's daughter company "IHP Solutions". IHP plans as well to exploit the results academically via its annual summer school, and lectures given at Universities in Berlin and the graduate school supporting PhD students at IHP.

UPC is going to exploit its participation in BeGREEN project in order to further strengthen its ability to pursue research, development and teaching activities both for its own benefit and for the benefit of its country and the EU in general. In particular, the obtained expertise is expected to be applied to: (i) bring the forefront of technological development into their syllabuses to educate future engineers. (ii) Carry out doctoral and post-doctoral research in areas related to the project and, thanks to the cooperation between academia and industry during the project, foster the participation in programs such as Marie Skłodowska-Curie European Industrial Doctorate to help PhD candidates step outside academia. (iii) To improve the UPC's postgraduate and customized training courses, facilitating the convergence between research departments and public or private companies. (iv) To get aligned with the strategy for Horizon Europe 2021-2027 and stay competitive for future research initiatives in different domains (national programme, etc.).

ACC is an SME focusing on cloud-native Open RAN network functions (Near-RT RIC and CU) and RAN integration, especially targeted toward newer private and shared RAN (neutral host) 5G networks. The eco-system developed in BeGREEN and the resultant energy-saving capabilities will enable distinct competitive advantages (in OPEX savings from energy reduction) for ACC products and solutions and hence increased SOM (Serviceable Obtainable Market, or market share). This will drive both shorter-term 5G-Advanced sales (e.g., the efficient ARM and accelerated hardware, RIC xApp driven energy-saving) and longer-term 6G (with RIS, distributed MIMO) roadmap of products. Monitoring of shorter-term commercial opportunities will be

a priority for an SME such as ACC. The BeGREEN results, through TCO (Total cost of Ownership) reductions, will unlock new verticals and applications for Open B5G/6G solutions, increasing TAM (Total Addressable Market). Resultant BeGREEN competitive advantages will increase the SAM (Serviceable Available Market) through improved TCO (Total Cost of Ownership) for these new verticals and as ‘greener’ alternatives for current verticals (like Industrial/Enterprise private networks, shared dense urban deployments, etc.).

GIGASYS is an SME on wireless consultancy and project management in the area of collaborative R&D in ICT. GIGASYS will use selected BeGREEN results for strengthening its consulting competency and to deliver value to its clients in the telecommunications industry across Europe. The exploitation of BeGREEN results by GIGASYS follows a three-step process: i) Identification of exploitable project results on a continuous basis by GIGASYS’ key personnel; ii) Generation of White Papers and other information items based on the identified exploitable project results; iii) Value creation for clients through discussions, follow-up research and innovation as well as consulting on emerging networks, services, and applications related to the identified exploitable project results. In particular, GIGASYS will advise its telco clients and partners via bi- and multi-lateral exchanges, targeted workshops, and community-internal White Papers. Furthermore, GIGASYS will use BeGREEN results to advise its clients on opportunities and risks arising from BeGREEN results and the impact they may have.

REL is an SME considered a centre of excellence for OFDMA technology, REL develops the Sparq-2025 family of hardware (FPGA) accelerators for 5G O-RUs and O-DUs that reduces the 5G Network latency below 1 millisecond and enable UE position measurement accuracy of 1 cm level. REL also developed an E2E 5G network that is currently being deployed in a Sport Stadium in Israel. REL participated in four Horizon 2020 projects (IoRL, 5Genesis, Affordable 5G and 6G Brains) and was awarded the Innovation Radar award from the EU. REL will enhance the performance of its RU and DU solutions with the BeGREEN research results in terms of power radiation, power efficiency and power consumption.

5.2 Joint exploitation plans

Opportunities for joint exploitation of project results will be analysed throughout the project, as part of the work in T6.4. However, the BeGREEN consortium already incorporates partners that have an existing track record of collaboration, which paves the way for additional joint exploitations beyond the project lifetime. At the time of proposal writing four areas of potential joint exploitation have already been identified and are depicted in Figure 5-1 below. We describe these potential Joint Exploitation (JE) areas in brief:

Figure 5-1 Identified areas of BeGREEN's joint exploitation

JE-1: DU/RU offloading engine using GPU acceleration: The main stakeholders for this area are PW, REL, and ARM, which are the main partners contributing to T3.1 and T3.2 (see Section 3). PW, REL and ARM already have commercial relationships that will expedite the exploitation of any joint outcome developed in these tasks through any of their pre-existing projects. Another avenue for joint exploitation in this area are joint contributions to SDOs, e.g., O-RAN alliance.

- **JE-2:** O-RAN Intelligent Plane. The main stakeholders in this area are LMI, I2CAT, and ACC, which are the main partners working on T4.1 (see Section 3). I2CAT and ACC have a long track record of collaboration in previous 5GPPP projects, such as 5G-CITY, 5G-CLARITY and Affordable5G. Through these collaborations I2CAT has developed software solutions that can be integrated with ACC's dRAX product, such as O-RAN non-RT RIC or other orchestration components. A joint exploitation of the developed O-RAN related assets beyond the project could be explored either through direct license transfer agreements between I2CAT and ACC, or through market collaborations between ACC and Neutron (www.neutron.com), which is an I2CAT spin-off commercializing management system for private 5G networks. LMI has a product line related to OSS and energy efficiency features in B5G/6G that could benefit from a partnership with ACC to introduce O-RAN technology in this market.

JE-3: O-RAN Controlled RIS. The main stakeholders in this area are IHP, I2CAT, and NEC which are the main stakeholders in T3.3 (c.f. Section3). NEC and I2CAT are previous collaborators, and with IHP they have been in previous 5GPP projects, e.g., and 5G-CITY, 5G-CLARITY. An avenue for joint exploitation is to use the collaborations in BeGREEN to improve NECs current RIS product and evolve its data-driven product portfolio taking into account the benefits of AI and ML, and to upgrade the product to a sensing/radar information assisted RIS to optimize its operation.

JE-4: Next Generation Edge. The main stakeholders in this area are NEC, I2CAT and ACC, which are the main stakeholders in T4.3 (c.f. Section3). These partners have been closely collaborated previously as stated in the above bullets. The target here is the collaborative developments on the O-RAN based next-generation edge where again an area of exploitation of the developed O-RAN related assets would be through could be explored e.g., through direct license transfer agreements between I2CAT, ACC, and NEC, or through market collaboration.

5.3 Innovation and IPR management strategy

An important indicator of the project success is how the innovation resulting from the project's main results is tailored to the market needs and can be directly adopted by stakeholders active in the specific market. This is actively addressed in BeGREEN by supporting the developers' perspective, and the high entrepreneurship attitude of many partners in the consortium with expertise in the formation of start-ups and profitable companies. This is further supported by the strong individual and joint exploitation opportunities described in Section 5.1 and Section 5.2. To foster these BeGREEN ambitious goals, the Innovation Manager (IM) will ensure the appropriate knowledge and results from BeGREEN can be transformed into services and products for the market. The IM will oversee managing and monitoring the innovation process in the project, across all the various technical WPs and to establish all the available channels to shortcut the research project results and the target market. Specific actions that will promote exploitation of BeGREEN innovations include:

Dialogue with the industrial community and project end customers (media and network operators). It is vital for this project to really address the right problems as perceived by the stakeholders. This means the voice of the private tenants and operators are of paramount importance. The IM will tightly interact with the External Advisory Board to validate requirements, problems, and solutions for the private venues connectivity as they will emerge from the initial design steps in BeGREEN. At least five meetings over the 30

months duration of the project will be organized with the External Advisory Board, one per first and second year face to face the rest remotely via videoconference, with specific sessions on innovation potentials and actions of the project.

Active project representation at relevant meetings, public events, and exhibitions, such as for example the Mobile World Congress (MWC), 5G World Forum, 5G Week, etc., to showcase BeGREEN solutions and establish preliminary channels for business development with vendors and operators.

Dialogue with the project's stakeholders, technical experts, and influencers, via social media presence (Twitter and/or blog posts, LinkedIn group, etc.), with frequent news updates to increase the online visibility of the project and its results, and to widely announce its activities and results.

Maintenance of a registry of potential BeGREEN innovative solutions that can originate products and may need patenting. The registry will be complemented by the development of Business Model Canvas in T6.4 to summarize market potentials and resources needed to build profitable business out of these results.

Dedicated innovation management task within WP6. The Innovation Manager will steer and establish a series of specific activities to share, educate and foster the daily-work deployment of agile innovation management methodologies and industry best practices. The rationale is to increase the innovation capabilities of researchers and project managers of the consortium. The final scope is to introduce methods that will facilitate an effective exploitation of the new ideas and concepts of the project, spotlessly and effectively steering them towards the different phases of products creation (design, implementation, PoC, demonstration, market launch).

6 Summary and Conclusions

This document has described BeGREEN's plan on dissemination and communication actions, the individual and joint exploitation activities, the envisaged liaisons and the standardization contribution plan. Although these plans are subject to modifications, they constitute the framework of reference that will drive the coordination, implementation, and supervision of BeGREEN dissemination and communication activities. Also, they ensure that BeGREEN achievements are widely spread over the BeGREEN target audience to enhance the project's impact and visibility to the European Union (EU) and the entire world.

The project identifier, the communication activities that will be carried out in the BeGREEN project throughout its lifetime, the external/internal communication channels, and social media have been defined in the communication plan. For internal communications of the partners, the project consortium uses MS Teams as the repository and collaboration tool. As a principal external communication channel, a project website has been developed and is ready to be launched. Besides, social media accounts (i.e., Twitter, LinkedIn, and YouTube), which are accessible from the project website, have been created to enhance the visibility of the project and to distribute the potential benefits derived from the solutions proposed in the project.

This document also presents the dissemination plan to communicate the project outcomes to the Industry, Academia, and the public in general. The key envisaged activities in this regard are the production of scientific publications in leading international conferences and journals, the organization of journal/magazines special issues and books, and the participation in program committees and editorial boards. Furthermore, project's liaison plan, specially with SNS community and its working groups, are outlined and representatives are identified.

Regarding the standardization plan, this deliverable identifies the primary SDOs whose activities are aligned with the project. Specifically, the SDOs considered are 3GPP, ETSI, and O-RAN Alliance. The standardization plan includes a roadmap that captures the standardization activities that may influence or get influenced by the project's technological innovations. It also describes the leading open-source related activities and the expected contributions to them where applicable.

Finally, this document summarizes the preliminary, individual and joint, exploitation plans. These plans, although premature at this early stage of the project, will be the baseline for project's Innovation Manager to work with partners on its evolution toward a comprehensive plan.

Further, updated plans on dissemination, communication, exploitation and standardisation contributions, together with tangible results, will be subsequently reported in D6.2 (Interim report on exploitation – due in M12), D6.3 (Interim report on dissemination and communication – due in M13), D6.4 (Interim report on standardisation contribution – due in M18), D6.5 (Final report on dissemination, impact, and exploitation – due in M30) and D6.6 (Software contribution to open-source projects – due in M30).

Bibliography

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